

Transitioning to Digital Assessment: Student Readiness and Challenges Encountered in the First Computer-Based National Standardized Examinations at LCC-Bais

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ABSTRACT

Assessment is at the heart of the teaching-learning process. While technology integration is no longer a new concept in education, the gradual digitalization of the assessment systems in the country warrants close attention. This study investigated the perceived levels of readiness and the challenges encountered by Grade 10 and Grade 12 students in the first computer-based National Career Assessment Examination (NCAE) and National Achievement Test (NAT). Anchored in Parasuraman's Technology Readiness, Sweller et al.'s Cognitive Load, and Spielberger's Anxiety Theory, the researchers employed descriptive-comparative methods and adapted survey questionnaires in data gathering. The participants were fifty-six (56) Grade 12 and twelve (12) Grade 10 students, who were selected through convenience sampling.

The Grade 10 and Grade 12 students have exhibited moderate levels of perceived technological and procedural readiness for the computer-based NCAE and NAT. However, psychological readiness was found to be low in both grade levels due to heightened anxiety and performance expectations associated with the examination. Poor internet connectivity emerged as the most prevalent technological challenge. In terms of procedural challenges, time management during the examination proved difficult, compounded by insufficient orientation and unclear instructions. The respondents also faced psychological challenges, including anxiety about finishing the test within the allotted time among Grade 10 students and the pressure of obtaining favorable results among Grade 12 students. While the Grade 10 students tend to be less psychologically prepared than their Grade 12 counterparts, the number of challenges they encountered during the CBT remained comparable. Ultimately, the computer-based NCAE and NAT posed demands and challenges that require institutional and department-wide interventions. In support of SDG 4, national education goals, and the objectives of LCC-Bais, an orientation guide for computer-based NAT and NCAE test-takers at LCC-Bais was developed.

KEYWORDS: *NAT, NCAE, Computer-based Test, Student Readiness, Challenges*

INTRODUCTION

Student assessment is central to the teaching-learning process. Educators utilize students' assessments to track the progress of learners. Its importance goes beyond the four walls of the classroom as curriculum development is deeply rooted in it. Utilizing the results of student assessment, educational institutions have identified learning gaps and implemented data-driven interventions.

From a global perspective, standardized examinations, such as the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), are seen as catalysts to improve standards. PISA results have prompted governments all around the world to benchmark the best practices of high-ranking education systems (Del Rosario & Santos, 2024). National examinations, such as the National Achievement Test (NAT) and the National Career Assessment Examination (NCAE), have complemented international student assessments in monitoring student readiness and performance.

The NAT is a standardized examination administered by the Department of Education (DepEd) to Grades 6 and 12 students to assess their academic performance at key stages. NAT results reveal the extent to which learners master the prescribed competencies. DepEd Order No. 55 s. 2016 emphasizes that the NAT plays a vital role in monitoring the quality of education. Simply put, it helps the education sector in recognizing areas needing improvement in both public and private schools in the country (EDCOM II, 2026). In contrast, the NCAE is a prospective aptitude test, as it focuses on future pathways. It guides students in making educational and career choices. DepEd Memo 115 s. 2012 underscores the importance of NCAE in minimizing the mismatch between skills and job market demands (Benito, n.d.).

Although different in purpose and in scope, the NAT and NCAE share a common method of test administration. Both examinations were traditionally administered using pen and paper. Students were made to answer the structured questions that are printed on standardized booklets or test sheets. This testing method has been widely used in large-scale national assessments since the 90s. However, along with its implementation are several challenges and obstacles. Systematic reviews done by Cuyag et al. (2024) and Reyno and Guzman (2025) have documented long waiting times, processing errors, and logistical constraints. Both these pressing issues and global demands have prompted the education sector to revamp the standardized examinations through ICT integration, particularly Computer-based Testing (CBT).

The United States is one of the first implementers of CBT. From the traditional paper-and-pencil style, national and state examinations were converted to a computerized format. This method soon expanded to standardized and internationally recognized assessments, with ACCUPLACER as one of its pioneering implementers (Sternin et al., 2019). In Asia, Japan and Singapore are considered two of the first few adopters of the computer-based examinations (Shobo, 2007; as cited in Nimi and Matsura, 2022). Its implementation has led to significant improvements in assessment efficiency, security, and scalability.

While CBT is no longer a new concept in the global arena, the gradual digitalization of the assessment systems in the Philippines warrants close attention. Pursuant to DM 108 s. 2025 and DM 14 s. 2026, public and private schools conducted the CBTs for NCAE and NAT before the end of SY 2025-2026. Although nothing has changed much relative to the content of the exam, existing theories and models suggest that dimensions such as technological readiness, procedural readiness, and psychological readiness are worth investigating. Little is known about the implementation of CBT at the school level, particularly in LCC-Bais. Likewise, empirical evidence on student readiness for taking the NAT and NCAE through CBT reveals a gap that this study intends to address.

Aligned with this purpose, the researchers intend to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of perceived readiness of Grade 10 and Grade 12 students in the computer-based test in terms of:
 - 1.1 Technological readiness
 - 1.2 Procedural readiness
 - 1.3 Psychological readiness
2. What are the challenges encountered by Grade 10 and Grade 12 students during the computer-based test in terms of:
 - 2.1 Technological challenges
 - 2.2 Procedural challenges
 - 2.3 Psychological challenges
3. Is there a significant difference in the perceived readiness of students when grouped according to grade level (Grade 10 and Grade 12)?
4. Is there a significant difference in the number of challenges encountered by students when grouped according to grade level (Grade 10 and Grade 12)?

The variables of this study are anchored in three (3) theoretical dimensions, namely: Parasuraman's Technology Readiness, Sweller et al.'s Cognitive Load, and Spielberger's Anxiety Theory.

Technology Readiness, according to Parasuraman, refers to the individual's willingness and confidence in adopting technological innovations. Parasuraman asserts that technology readiness is determined by both promoting and inhibiting factors. Optimism and innovativeness are considered promoters, while discomfort and insecurity are viewed as inhibitors. In the context of this study, students' readiness for CBT is achieved when the positive drivers outweigh the barriers. Operationally, technological readiness refers to the willingness and confidence of the Grade 10 and 12 students in adopting computer-based testing methods.

Meanwhile, Sweller et al.'s Cognitive Load Theory posits that three cognitive loads affect an individual's mental processes, namely: intrinsic, extraneous, and germane. The theory defines intrinsic workload as the innate difficulty of the task. Extraneous load, on the other hand, refers to the environmental factors that may either facilitate or distract individuals. In contrast, the effort that contributes directly to learning is termed as germane cognitive load (Clark & Kimmons, 2023). In the context of this study, procedural readiness is defined as students' competence in using the computer-based testing platform. In addition, it also refers to their ability to effectively perform

the processes and tasks required in computer-based testing. The students' procedural readiness is affected by the demands of extraneous loads, such as navigating interfaces, interpreting on-screen instructions, and managing the allotted time for CBT.

This study has also found anchorage in the State-Trait Anxiety Theory of Spielberger. The theory asserts that anxiety has two (2) dimensions, trait and state. While state anxiety is a temporary emotion that only occurs in response to or anticipation of stressful situations, trait anxiety is a tendency to feel anxious across many situations. (West, M., 2022). These assertions have led to the development of the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI), which is a widely used instrument that allows one to measure the anxiety of an individual (Radar for Leaders, n.d.). When applied to computer-based NAT and NCAE, psychological readiness refers to the mental and emotional preparedness of students to participate in computer-based testing. Both the theory and the tool guide researchers in assessing how prepared students are mentally and emotionally for CBT.

Taken together, the theories of Technology Readiness, Cognitive Load, and State-Trait Anxiety provide a holistic framework for analyzing students' readiness and challenges in the computer-based NAT and NCAE.

In light of the theories discussed, the researchers came up with the conceptual framework as shown below.

Figure 1. *Conceptual Framework of the Study*

An Input–Process–Output (IPO) framework is used to examine students’ readiness and challenges in the computer-based test (CBT) of NAT and NCAE. The input includes Grade 10 and Grade 12 students’ perceived technological, procedural, and psychological readiness, as well as the challenges they encountered. The data will be obtained through an online survey and will be analyzed statistically to determine levels and differences by grade level. The output serves as a basis for improving CBT implementation, including the development of a CBT orientation guide.

As shown in the framework, the students’ perceived level of readiness and challenges are assessed in terms of technological, procedural, and psychological dimensions. It does not include the content dimension, given that the 2026 computer-based NAT and NCAE cover similar competencies as the previous NAT and NCAE delivered through pen and paper. Moreover, since the students have already taken the CBT, readiness as a construct will be assessed retrospectively. Thus, students will simply reflect on how prepared they were before they took the CBT.

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized both descriptive and comparative methods in quantitative research. Descriptive research is a type of quantitative research design that describes a population, situation, or phenomenon without manipulation or intervention. Meanwhile, the comparative research identifies similarities and differences between various aspects of the study. In the current study, the data for the perceived level of readiness and the challenges encountered were presented and analyzed descriptively. The researchers also compared the results obtained from the participating Grades 10 and 12 students.

The study took place in La Consolacion College, Bais City. The actual CBTs for NCAE and NAT were conducted on February 14 and March 18-24, 2026, respectively. Having the necessary computer units and internet connectivity, the computer laboratory of the institution served as the official testing venue of the examinations. The photos of students taking the CBTs for NAT and NCAE can be seen in Appendix A.

Respondents, Population, and Sampling

The eligible population of the study consisted of 109 Grade-12 Senior High School students and 20 Grade-10 students who were enrolled during the School Year 2025–2026. All of these students had taken either the NAT (for Grade 12) or the NCAE (for Grade 10). The researchers initially planned to employ complete enumeration to ensure data accuracy and better representation of the students. However, as the Grade 10 and 12 students had already moved up or graduated at the time of the data collection, not all students were accessible. Hence, convenience sampling was used. The sample size was determined using the Rule of Majority. Fifty-six (56) Grade 12 and twelve (12) Grade 10 students, representing 51% and 60% of the respective grades, participated in the study.

Instrumentation, Validation, and Reliability

The researchers adapted three publicly available standardized research instruments to measure the variables of the study. The instruments include: namely, the Technology Readiness Index, Computer Self-Efficacy Scale, and the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI).

The **Technology Readiness Index (TRI)** of Parasuraman is a widely used model for measuring individuals' readiness to adopt and use new technologies. The items in this tool are centered on the promoters and inhibitors of technological readiness. This tool has guided researchers in assessing students' readiness for CBT, as manifested through their confidence, willingness, adaptability, and optimism.

Higgins' Computer Self-Efficacy Scale (CSES) is a psychological measurement tool used to assess how individuals perceive their competence in using computers and other forms of technology. The CSES has been used in multiple contexts, such as education, workplace training, and systems development. In relation to the present study, the items of the CSES are deemed relevant because CBT similarly requires students to possess competence in using digital platforms. Having this tool as a guide, researchers were able to measure the students' perceived ability to use computers effectively.

The **State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI)**, on the other hand, was developed in 1970 by Charles D. Spielberger. This instrument measures the anxiety levels of an individual. This tool has guided researchers in assessing students' psychological readiness and challenges in relation to their unfamiliarity with digital testing platforms and the pressure associated with computerized examinations.

Adapting the above-mentioned instrument means that researchers have modified and contextualized the existing items. Doing so enabled the researchers to align the instrument to its intended respondents. The items in the questionnaire are structured as a Likert scale. The questionnaire is divided into two main sections: readiness and challenges. Each main section has three sub-sections: the technological, procedural, and psychological domains. Each sub-section is composed of 8 items. The researchers sought three experts to validate the researcher-modified questionnaire. The experts who took part in the validation procedure were as follows: 1.) a registered psychometrician, 2.) an IT expert who served as the CBT technical or system implementer, and 3.) a Teacher-Implementer of CBT in the School's Division of Bais City. Utilizing the institutional validation tool for survey instrument, an average rating of 3.2 was obtained, indicating that the instrument is recommended for use after specific revisions. A pilot test was also done among 20 SHS students who are non-participants of the actual data gathering. The Cronbach's alpha of 0.87 revealed the reliability of the researcher-modified instrument.

Data Gathering Procedure and Analysis

After successful validation and pilot testing, the survey questionnaire was floated via Google Forms. The link was sent through the students' existing chat groups in Messenger. Ethical principles were observed throughout the data-gathering process. For minors, consent from their parents was obtained before the actual survey. For participants who were of legal age, informed consent was likewise secured prior to their participation. Pursuant to the Data Privacy Act, the responses obtained were treated confidentially. The files were only accessible to the researchers. The responses were devoid of the participants' personal information, such as their names. The students were assured that their participation was voluntary and that they may withdraw at any time without any penalty. The data-gathering process was completed within 7 days. The data obtained were coded in MS Excel and treated using both descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, weighted means) and inferential statistics (Mann-Whitney U and Independent t-test). For the level of student readiness, the interpretation was patterned after the study of Linjawi and Alfadda (2018), using the following scale ranges: 1.00–1.75 (No Readiness), 1.76–2.50 (Low), 2.51-3.25 (Moderate) and 3.26–4.00 (High).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. *Grade 10 Students' Perceived Level of Readiness for Computerized NCAE*

Dimensions	Weighted Mean	Verbal description
Technological Readiness		
I am confident that the computer-based test (CBT) improves the examination process.	2.42	Disagree
I can adapt to changes in new testing technologies, such as the computer-based test (CBT).	2.67	Agree
I feel paper-based examinations are more reliable than computer-based tests (CBT).	3.25	Strongly Agree
I am willing to try new technologies in education.	3.08	Agree
I have tried using digital tools and platforms in answering quizzes in my class before.	2.67	Agree
I am open to using CBT even if I am more familiar with paper-based tests.	2.75	Agree
I look for opportunities to use new technologies in academic tasks.	3.00	Agree
*I doubt the reliability of computer-based systems in recording answers accurately.	2.33	Agree
Composite WM	2.77	Agree
<i>Level of Technological Readiness: Moderate</i>		

Procedural Readiness		
I am able to handle minor technical issues during computer-based test (CBT).	2.50	Disagree
I can use the keyboard and mouse efficiently during computer-based tests (CBT).	3.33	Strongly Agree
I can handle the basic actions required for computer-based testing.	3.25	Strongly Agree
I can move between test questions without difficulty.	2.58	Agree
*I have difficulty understanding directions given by computer-based testing systems.	2.58	Agree
I can finish computer-based tests within the allotted time (CBT).	2.58	Agree
I can apply problem-solving strategies effectively during computer-based tests.	2.92	Agree
I can analyze questions efficiently during computer-based tests (CBT).	2.83	Agree
Composite WM	2.82	Agree
<i>Level of Procedural Readiness: Moderate</i>		
Psychological Readiness		
I can maintain emotional stability when using computer-based testing platforms.	3.08	Agree
I am able to avoid mental blocks during computer-based tests (CBT).	2.75	Agree
*I feel pressured when the timer is running.	1.58	Strongly Agree
*I tend to worry about making mistakes during CBT exams.	1.67	Strongly Agree
*I worry that I might lose my answers due to technical issues.	1.25	Strongly Agree
I do not worry about my performance in computer-based tests (CBT)	2.08	Disagree
*I tend to overthink possible bad scenarios during an exam.	1.67	Strongly Agree
*I generally feel uneasy during examinations	2.00	Agree
Composite WM	2.01	Disagree
<i>Level of Psychological Readiness: Low</i>		
General WM	2.53	AGREE
<i>Overall Level of Readiness: MODERATE</i>		

Table 1 presents the Grade 10 Students' perceived level of readiness during the computerized National Career Assessment Examination (NCAE). It is divided into three dimensions: the Technological Readiness, Procedural Readiness, and Psychological Readiness. The overall assessment yields a General Weighted Mean (GWM) of 2.53, which corresponds to the descriptive interpretation of "Agree." This indicates that Grade 10 Students possess a Moderate Level of Readiness for the transition from traditional paper-based to a Computer-Based Test (CBT).

The dimension of technological readiness obtained a composite weighted mean (WM) of 2.77, verbally described as "Agree," indicating a moderate level of technological readiness. The highest mean score of 3.25 revealed that Grade 10 students believe paper-based examinations are more reliable than computer-based tests (CBT). However, the students expressed doubts that the computer-based test (CBT) can improve the examination process. Furthermore, the lowest mean score in this dimension was 2.33, which means that students actively worry whether the computer system can record their answers accurately. This dimension yielded a composite weighted mean of 2.77, indicating the students' moderate level of perceived technological readiness. The findings indicate that while Grade 10 students are highly open-minded and willing to try new technological

tools, they still carry deep concerns about whether the technology is reliable. The result is consistent with the observations of Pengelley et. al (2024), who noted that while educational institutions push for computerized testing, students often encounter low productive outcomes due to the lack of trust regarding how software tools process their inputs.

In the second dimension, the composite weighted mean (WM) of 2.82 indicated a moderate level of procedural awareness among Grade 10 students. The highest mean score within this dimension was 3.33 (“Strongly Agree”), indicating that Grade 10 students can use the keyboard and mouse efficiently during the computer-based test (CBT). This is followed closely by their ability to handle the basic actions required for computer-based testing (WM = 3.25, “Strongly Agree”). However, the Grade 10 students also agreed that they experience difficulty understanding directions given by computer-based testing systems (WM = 2.58, “Agree”). Conversely, the lowest scores in the procedural readiness, which was a mean of 2.50 indicate that Grade 10 Students do not feel they can easily handle minor technical issues during computer-based tests (CBT). The results on procedural readiness show that Grade 10 students are highly capable of basic computer navigation and handling of technological tools such as keyboard and mouse. However, they are easily affected when they encounter system glitches or technical errors during computer-based testing. This finding is in line with a study by Zakariya et al. (2026) that used the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), they found that even in cases where students are good with computers, regular problems such as server crashes and malfunctioning equipment make computer-based tests far more difficult to use.

For the psychological readiness dimension, the composite weighted mean of 2.01 indicated that Grade 10 students possess a Low Level of Psychological Readiness toward Computer-Based Testing (CBT). The lowest mean score in this dimension is 1.25, revealing that students worry they might lose their answers during computer-based tests due to technical issues. This is followed closely by a strong fear of making mistakes during an exam (WM = 1.67), a tendency to overthink possible bad scenarios during an exam (WM = 1.67), and feeling heavily pressured by a running countdown timer (WM = 1.58). These negative indicators prove that Grade 10 students experience technological anxiety and emotional distress during computer-based testing. Additionally, the Grade 10 students generally feel uneasy during examinations (WM = 2.00), expressing worries about their performance in computer-based tests (WM = 2.08). The findings indicate that despite the student’s efforts to maintain focus and prevent mental blocks, the digital testing environment gives them psychological pressure. The data finds vindication in the study of Zakariya et al. (2026), who highlighted that CBT features such as a visible countdown timer act as an immediate distraction, making students feel rushed and emotionally unstable. This is also heavily supported by the Cognitive Load Theory as highlighted by Pengelley et. al (2024), who detailed that the psychological experience of testing mode can overload a student’s working memory. Thus, while students possess the basic technical skills to answer test questions, the psychological burden of strict time limits and unpredictable system errors causes them to perceive a low level of psychological readiness.

Table 2. Grade 12 Students' Perceived Level of Readiness for Computerized NAT

Dimensions	Weighted Mean	Verbal description
Technological Readiness		
I am confident that the computer-based test (CBT) improves the examination process.	2.88	Agree
I can adapt to changes in new testing technologies, such as the computer-based test (CBT).	3.09	Agree
I feel paper-based examinations are more reliable than computer-based tests (CBT).	2.52	Agree
I am willing to try new technologies in education.	2.93	Agree
I have tried using digital tools and platforms in answering quizzes in my class before.	2.93	Agree
I am open to using CBT even if I am more familiar with paper-based tests.	2.93	Agree
I look for opportunities to use new technologies in academic tasks.	2.96	Agree
*I doubt the reliability of computer-based systems in recording answers accurately.	2.30	Agree
Composite WM	2.82	Agree
Level of Technological Readiness: Moderate		
Procedural Readiness		
I am able to handle minor technical issues during computer-based test (CBT).	2.70	Agree
I can use the keyboard and mouse efficiently during computer-based tests (CBT).	2.98	Agree
I can handle the basic actions required for computer-based testing.	3.07	Agree
I can move between test questions without difficulty.	2.89	Agree
*I have difficulty understanding directions given by computer-based testing systems.	2.62	Disagree
I can finish computer-based tests within the allotted time (CBT).	2.71	Agree
I can apply problem-solving strategies effectively during computer-based tests.	2.88	Agree
I can analyze questions efficiently during computer-based tests (CBT).	3.04	Agree
Composite WM	2.86	Agree
Level of Procedural Readiness: Moderate		
Psychological Readiness		
I can maintain emotional stability when using computer-based testing platforms.	2.96	Agree
I am able to avoid mental blocks during computer-based tests (CBT).	2.66	Agree
*I feel pressured when the timer is running.	1.77	Agree
*I tend to worry about making mistakes during CBT exams.	1.84	Agree
*I worry that I might lose my answers due to technical issues.	1.84	Agree
I do not worry about my performance in computer-based tests (CBT)	2.54	Agree
*I tend to overthink possible bad scenarios during an exam.	1.98	Agree
*I generally feel uneasy during examinations	2.11	Agree
Composite WM	2.21	Disagree
Level of Psychological Readiness: Low		
General WM	2.63	Agree
Overall Level of Readiness: MODERATE		

The Grade 12 students' perceived levels of readiness for the Computerized National Achievement Test (NAT) are shown in Table 2. Student readiness is assessed in three dimensions: technological, procedural, and psychological.

For the first dimension, the composite weighted mean of 2.82 reveals a moderate level of technological readiness among Grade 12 students. This indicates that students are generally confident in using digital tools when taking standardized tests. The highest weighted mean for this dimension reflects the students' ability to adapt to new testing technologies (WM = 3.09). Despite their willingness to adapt, students still have doubts about the reliability of computer-based systems in recording their answers accurately (WM=2.30).

In terms of procedural readiness, the findings suggest that students are capable of handling the basic tasks for computer-based testing (WM=3.07) and using the keyboard and mouse efficiently (WM=2.98). It is also worth noting that the Grade 12 students have expressed confidence in their ability to manage minor technical issues (WM=2.70) and understand testing instructions (WM=2.62). Taken together, the composite weighted mean of 2.86 demonstrates a moderate level of perceived procedural readiness among Grade 12 students in taking the computerized NAT

In terms of psychological readiness, the composite weighted mean of 2.01 (low level of readiness) highlights a significant concern. Although students have expressed their ability to remain emotionally stable (WM = 2.96), the mere thought of an upcoming computer-based test (CBT) makes them feel anxious (WM= 1.84) and worried (WM= 1.84). The lowest weighted mean of 1.77 also reveals a significant pressure felt by students in relation to time constraints.

Overall, the Grade 12 students are moderately prepared for the computerized NAT, especially in terms of technological and procedural readiness. In contrast, the Grade 12 students' readiness was found to be the weakest in terms of the psychological dimension. These findings suggest that while students possess the necessary technological skills and procedural knowledge to participate in computer-based examinations, they may experience challenges related to their emotional and mental preparedness. The findings have found anchorage in the study of Scheel et al. (2022), wherein students, despite adequate technological skills for computer-based examinations, still experience anxiety and uncertainty before taking digital assessments. Furthermore, computer-based test anxiety has been found to negatively affect both the students' confidence and performance in computerized examinations, despite having sufficient computer skills (Balogun & Olanrewaju, 2016).

Table 3. Challenges encountered by Grade 10 students during the computerized NCAE

Challenges	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Technological Challenges			
Difficulty logging into the system	4	33.33	4
Malfunctioning of the computer (e.g. errors, freezing, lagging)	6	50.00	2
Poor internet connectivity	7	58.33	1
Unfamiliarity with the platform	5	41.67	3
Procedural Challenges			
Difficulty in managing the time	11	91.67	1
Difficulty in submitting answers	6	50.00	4
Lack of proper orientation and/or unclear instructions	9	75.00	2
Difficulty in changing the answer after selecting a response.	5	41.67	5
Difficulty in reviewing previous answers.	8	66.67	3
Psychological Challenges			
Difficulty in concentrating during the exam.	8	66.67	3
Pressure due to the time limit.	11	91.67	1
Doubt in one's ability to answer correctly.	7	58.33	4
Pressure of securing good results	9	75.00	2
Mental blockage when answering difficult questions.	6	50.00	5

The challenges encountered by the Grade 10 students during the computer-based NCAE are shown in the table above. Among the technological challenges, poor internet connectivity (58.33%) was the most frequently experienced problem, which affected the majority of the respondents. This was followed by computer malfunctions affecting half of the participating Grade 10 students. Meanwhile, unfamiliarity with the platform and difficulty logging in were less common issues during the computer-based NCAE. In light of Sweller's Theory, connectivity issues and computer malfunctioning may have increased the students' cognitive load. These issues may have adversely affected students' concentration and performance in the computer-based NCAE.

In terms of procedural challenges, the difficulty in managing time emerged as the most significant concern, affecting nearly all respondents (91.67%). Ranked second and third are the lack of proper orientation or unclear instructions (75.00%) and difficulty in reviewing previous answers (66.67%), respectively. Thus, students' performance may have been adversely affected not only due to the actual content of the assessment but also because of the operational demands of the computer-based platform. For psychological challenges, pressure due to the time limit was found to be the most common issue, affecting 91.67% of the respondents. Moreover, the pressure to secure good results and the difficulty in concentrating during the examination also affected the majority of the respondents. These results imply that the students who took the NCAE were accompanied by considerable levels of anxiety. Such psychological strain may have influenced students' cognitive function, which ultimately affected their overall examination performance.

Taken together, the findings have shown that the Grade 10 students encountered various challenges during the computerized National Career Assessment Examination (NCAE), with procedural and psychological challenges being more prominent than technological issues. Similarly, Istiyono et al. (2023) have found that gaps in CBT preparation for CBTs, including time management, hinder students' ability to complete the assessment successfully. Meanwhile, the findings on psychological challenges are consistent with the study of Toquero (2020) wherein the transition to technology-mediated forms of assessment presents psychological demands on students that require significant adjustment and support.

Table 4. *Challenges encountered by Grade 12 students during the computerized NAT*

Challenges	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Technological Challenges			
Difficulty logging into the system	20	35.71	3
Malfunctioning of the computer (e.g. errors, freezing, lagging)	26	46.43	2
Poor internet connectivity	30	53.57	1
Unfamiliarity with the platform	18	32.14	4
Others	2	3.57	5
Procedural Challenges			
Difficulty in managing the time	24	42.86	1
Difficulty in submitting answers	10	17.86	3.5
Lack of proper orientation and/or unclear instructions	9	16.07	5
Difficulty in changing the answer after selecting a response.	10	17.86	3.5
Difficulty in reviewing previous answers.	11	19.64	2
Others	2	3.57	6
Psychological Challenges			
Difficulty in concentrating during the exam.	17	30.36	5
Pressure due to the time limit.	22	39.29	3
Doubt in one's ability to answer correctly.	21	37.50	4
Pressure of securing good results	26	46.43	1
Mental blockage when answering difficult questions.	23	41.07	2

Table 4 presents the challenges encountered by Grade 12 students during the administration of the computerized National Achievement Test (NAT). The challenges were categorized into technological, procedural, and psychological factors.

In terms of technological challenges, the most frequently reported challenge was poor internet connectivity. This concern has affected the majority of the respondents. This was followed by the malfunctioning of computers, such as system errors, freezing, and lagging, reported by 26 respondents (46.43%). Meanwhile, difficulty logging into the system and unfamiliarity with the testing platform were found to be relatively less common concerns. Disruptions in network access and computer functioning may compromise the administration of computer-based test.

These findings indicate that internet stability and computer functionality significantly affected students' testing experiences. It is therefore imperative for schools to prioritize improving network stability and maintaining functional computer units before administering CBTs.

Regarding procedural challenges, the table shows that almost half of the participating Grade 12 students encountered difficulty in managing time. Notably, the other procedural challenges, such as difficulty in reviewing, changing, and submitting answers, were only experienced by not more than 20% of the respondents. The results indicate that the allotted testing period, the length of the assessment, or students' pacing strategies may require attention. Meanwhile, the mechanics of taking the assessment, such as changing and submitting answers, are generally considered clear and easy to follow.

With respect to psychological challenges, the highest-ranked concern was the pressure of securing good results, which was reported by 26 respondents (46.43%). Ranked second and third are mental blockage when answering difficult questions (41.07%) and pressure due to the time limit (39.29%), respectively. Furthermore, doubt in one's ability to answer correctly was experienced by 37.50% of the respondents, while difficulty concentrating during the examination was reported by 30.36%. These findings reveal that many students experienced anxiety during the computerized NAT. Cognitive and emotional factors were present, which in turn have affected the student's overall testing experience. These findings reveal the need for interventions both before and after taking the CBTs.

The findings run parallel with the studies of Kunjiapu et al. (2025) and Barrot et al. (2021), wherein adjusting to new forms of technology and procedural unfamiliarity act as significant barriers to computer-based assessments. The abovementioned studies have also proven that poor internet connectivity disrupts students' focus, while insufficient orientation and practice lead to poor time management and contribute to test anxiety.

Table 5. *Mann-Whitney U Results on the Perceived Level of Readiness Between Grade 10 and Grade 12 Students*

Dimensions	Grade 10 Mean	Grade 12 Mean	Computed Value (U)	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Technological	2.77	2.82	278	0.35	Not Significant	Fail to Reject H ₀
Procedural	2.82	2.86	321	0.81	Not Significant	Fail to Reject H ₀
Psychological	2.01	2.21	491	0.01	Significant	Reject H ₀

Level of Significance = 0.05

Normality (Shapiro-Wilk Test) = <.001

This study investigated the difference between the Grade 10 and Grade 12 students' perceived level of readiness for the computer-based test (CBT). Since the data were found not to be normally distributed, as assessed using Shapiro-Wilk, a Mann-Whitney U test was used. The decision regarding the study's null hypothesis is based on a 0.05 level of significance.

Despite observable disparities in the technological and procedural readiness of the students, the statistical test yielded p-values greater than the level of significance. Statistically, a p-value that is higher than the significance level (5%) presents insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis of the study (McLeod, 2025). This means that perceived levels of technological and procedural readiness between Grade 10 and Grade 12 students do not significantly differ. The results further demonstrate that grade level alone may not be a determining factor in students' perceived levels of technological and procedural readiness. This has prompted the researchers to accept the null hypothesis of the study.

Interestingly, the statistical tool yielded a p-value of 0.01 for psychological readiness. This means that the students from the two grade levels significantly differ in their perceived level of psychological readiness. Based on the data, Grade 10 students have reported statistically lower perceived levels of psychological readiness compared to Grade 12 students, with a mean difference of 0.20. This means that Grade 12 students may feel more psychologically prepared or confident in taking CBTs compared to Grade 10 students. The significant results may be attributed to differences in emotional maturity, psychosocial support, academic pressures, and coping mechanisms. The result for psychological readiness has found anchorage in the study of Chao et al. (2024), wherein students who are typically younger are likely to experience increased anxiety related to computer-based tests.

Table 6. Results of the Independent Samples t-test on the Number of Challenges Encountered during the Computer-based Test between Grade 10 and Grade 12 Students

Challenges	Grade 10 Mean (SD)	Grade 12 Mean (SD)	Computed Value (t)	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Technological	2.17 (1.27)	1.58 (1.02)	1.50	0.15	Not Significant	Fail to Reject H ₀
Procedural	1.75 (1.29)	1.37 (0.83)	0.88	0.35	Not Significant	Fail to Reject H ₀
Psychological	2.92 (1.44)	2.11 (1.29)	1.79	0.09	Not Significant	Fail to Reject H ₀

Level of Significance = 0.05

Normality (Shapiro-Wilk Test) = >0.05

An independent samples t-test was carried out to determine whether significant differences exist in the number of challenges encountered by the Grade 10 and Grade 12 students during the computer-based test (CBTs).

As shown above, the Grade 10 students have reported a slightly higher number of challenges in their computer-based NCAE than the Grade 12 students during the computer-based NAT across all dimensions examined. According to McBride et al. (2024), it is possible for some students to experience greater difficulties with CBTs when they are younger or when they have less exposure to technology-assisted assessment modalities. These factors may have contributed to the higher number of challenges encountered by the Grade 10 students during the computer-based NCAE.

Despite notable variations, the p-values of 0.15, 0.35, and 0.09 indicate that the differences are merely attributed to chance and thus considered insignificant. This means that the Grade 10 and Grade 12 students experienced comparable technological, procedural, and psychological challenges during their CBTs. Therefore, it is insufficient to conclude that the two groups differ significantly in terms of the challenges they encountered, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. Albino and Agoja (2024) argue that the challenges encountered during CBTs may be similar across grade levels. As computer-based assessments become increasingly integrated into educational systems, students may develop similar levels of familiarity with CBTs regardless of grade level.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study investigated the perceived levels of readiness of Grade 10 and Grade 12 students in the first computer-based standardized national examinations. It also examined the technological, procedural, and psychological challenges encountered by the NAT and NCAE takers. The findings presented in the previous section revealed strengths, weaknesses, and identified points for institutional improvement.

The following conclusions were drawn from the study:

Firstly, the Grade 10 and Grade 12 students have demonstrated a moderate level of perceived readiness in taking the National Career Assessment Examination and the National Achievement Test. As supported by Parasuraman's Technology Readiness Theory, the students' optimism and willingness to adapt technology-assisted assessment methods have contributed to their technological readiness. Similarly, students' familiarity and competence in computer operations and hardware usage made CBTs appear less burdensome, as supported by the Cognitive Load Theory, making them procedurally prepared.

However, the psychological dimension emerged as the weakest area of readiness among students from both grade levels. Prior to taking the test, the students are generally troubled by the thought of time constraints, technical issues, and poor performance. These negative indicators prove that the Grade 10 and 12 students experience technological anxiety and emotional distress during computer-based testing. Anchored in the State-Trait Anxiety Theory, the study has proven that computer-based tests (CBTs) induce heightened anxiety and performance pressure among Grade 10 and Grade 12 students, which adversely affect their mental and emotional preparedness.

Secondly, the administration of computerized NCAE and NCAE is accompanied by a multitude of challenges that have affected the students' testing experience. Poor internet connectivity emerged as the most prevalent technological challenge encountered by the examination takers. In terms of procedural challenges, time management during the examination proved difficult for most students. Psychological pressures also affected both Grade 10 and Grade 12 students. However, the causes of pressure varied as Grade 10 students were more anxious about

finishing the exam within the allotted time, whereas Grade 12 students were primarily concerned about getting favorable examination results.

Thirdly, there was insufficient evidence that the grade level influences technological and procedural readiness. However, the Grade 10 students tend to be less psychologically prepared than their Grade 12 counterparts. As most literature suggests, students in higher grade levels generally exhibit greater emotional maturity, allowing them to better cope with the demands of standardized examinations. Lastly, the Grade 10 and Grade 12 students encountered a comparable number of technological, procedural, and psychological challenges during their computer-based tests, signifying that the issues associated with CBTs are neither developmental nor grade-specific.

Ultimately, the computerized NCAE and NAT both present demands and challenges that require institutional and department-wide interventions. In light of the study's conclusion, the following are the recommendations:

1. The Basic Education Department (BED), in collaboration with the ICT Department, should boost the technological and procedural readiness of students by enhancing digital literacy through the integration of computer-based activities and increased exposure to online testing platforms by teachers across all subject areas. Implementers of the CBT must provide proper orientation through clear, step-by-step explanations of test procedures, guidelines, and answering techniques on digital platforms to minimize confusion and ensure smooth test administration.
2. The Department of Education (DepEd) is encouraged to strengthen its support to the implementation of CBT by providing schools, including private educational institutions, with detailed pre-examination briefings and practice CBTs, orientation materials, and other capacity-building opportunities for both students and faculty members.
3. The guidance center is advised to offer mental preparation and psychological support services to students who are experiencing CBT-induced anxiety through stress management seminars, counseling sessions before major examinations, and confidence-building activities to help students perform better under pressure.
4. It is recommended that the school administration upgrade the school's ICT infrastructure and resources by ensuring functional computer units, stable internet connectivity, and conducive testing environments.
5. Future researchers are encouraged to examine additional factors influencing students' readiness for computerized assessments. Student readiness may also be correlated with their actual performance on the computerized NAT or NCAE. As the school implements measures to address the challenges identified in this study, future researchers are advised to conduct an evaluation study. Lastly, employing qualitative or mixed-method approaches in research to gain a deeper understanding of the CBT experience is also enjoined.

As an output of the study, an orientation guide for computer-based NAT and NCAE takers of LCC-Bais is proposed. The guide is presented in the succeeding pages.

Proposed CBT Orientation Guide for computer-based NAT and NCAE takers of LCC-Bais

Modules	Objectives	Topics covered	Activities	Persons in charge
Understanding CBTs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Define computer-based testing. 2. Identify common features of CBTs. 3. Compare and contrast paper-based and CBTs 4. Explain how responses are securely processed, saved, and recorded. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. What is a CBT? b. Common features c. Difference between paper-based and CBTs d. System reliability: How answers are saved and recorded 	Lecture	<p>Proctor/Examiner</p> <p>ICT Coordinator/ Computer Lab Technician</p>
Navigating the Platform	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Demonstrate proper login procedures. 2. Navigate the CBT interface. 3. Review, change, and submit answers properly. 4. Comply with on-screen instructions accurately. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Logging in b. Understanding on-screen instructions c. Navigating between questions d. Reviewing and Changing Answers e. Submitting responses 	Guided mock CBT session	<p>Proctor/Examiner</p> <p>ICT Coordinator/ Computer Lab Technician</p>
Managing Technical Issues	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify common technical issues during CBT administration. 2. Apply basic troubleshooting steps when confronted with technical issues. 3. Report technical procedures properly. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Common technical issues b. What to do when the computer freezes? c. What to do during internet interruptions? d. Reporting technical concerns 	Simulations	<p>Proctor/Examiner</p> <p>ICT Coordinator/ Computer Lab Technician</p>
Time Management Strategies	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Allocate appropriate time per item/section in the CBT. 2. Apply strategies to manage time during CBTs effectively. 3. Complete practice CBT questions within the time limit. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Time allocation per question b. Skip and return strategy c. Other test-taking strategies (e.g. Elimination) 	Timed-practice	<p>Adviser and Subject Teachers</p> <p>Proctor/Examiner</p> <p>Guidance Personnel</p>

Managing CBT-induced Anxiety	1. Recognize causes and effects of anxiety 2. Demonstrate coping strategies, relaxation, and confidence-building techniques during CBTs.	a. Understanding Anxiety: Causes and effects b. Coping with pressure, managing fear c. Concentration and confidence-building techniques	Guided relaxation exercises	Adviser and Subject Teachers Guidance Personnel
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